

Energy Transition Scenarios for Ecuador up to 2050: Modeling the Potential of Renewable Resources

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**Energy Modelling Platform Latin America and The
Caribbean (EMP-LAC) 2026**

Context

- The electricity matrix of Ecuador is highly dominated by hydroelectric generation (around 70–80%), which creates a strong dependence on the availability of water resources. This technological concentration limits the diversification of the system and makes it vulnerable to climatic variability, such as drought periods.
- Recent low-flow periods have reduced hydro generation to approximately 30–40% of its capacity and have produced deficits of several hundred megawatts. Studies project a loss of usable capacity of about 1,900–2,100 MW by 2050 in the five main hydroelectric plants (Naranjo & Quimbita, 2022).

Research Questions:

- **How does the gradual reduction of hydroelectric capacity in Ecuador’s power system influence the electricity sector under conditions of climatic variability and projected reductions in river flows caused by climate change?**
- **How is Ecuador’s electricity generation mix redistributed when hydroelectric capacity is constrained?**

Ecuador Reference Energy System

Methodology

1

- Reference energy system and data gathering

2

- Modeling and scenario analysis (OSeMOSYS)

3

- Result analysis and policy insights

Scenarios

Business-As-Usual (BAU)

No carbon target

Historical trends remain with limited penetration of non-conventional renewable

Minimum Cost (MIN)

The most cost-effective

- Prioritize the expansion of electricity generation technologies with a lower levelized cost of energy, primarily existing hydropower and economically competitive renewable technologies such as solar photovoltaics and wind power.
- Minimize the total cost of Ecuador's electric power system by ensuring energy supply and meeting projected demand at the lowest possible cost over the planning horizon.

Drought (DRO)

Reduction of hydro capacity factor by 2050

- The progressive 43% reduction is based on the observed decrease in hydropower generation between November 2022 and 2024 in Ecuador. This period was associated with droughts and reduced river flows, highlighting the vulnerability of the electricity system to climate variability.
- Explore to what extent the reduction in hydro creates room to expand solar, wind, biomass, and other renewable sources, improving the country's sustainability and energy security.

Results(1/3)

Electricity

Annual

Generation

Results(2/3)

Total
Installed
Capacity

Results(3/3)

By 2050

Conclusions & Policy Insights

Ecuador debe fortalecer políticas energéticas orientadas a la diversificación de la matriz eléctrica y a la reducción progresiva de la dependencia hidroeléctrica, con el fin de disminuir la vulnerabilidad del sistema frente a la variabilidad climática y los eventos de sequía. En este contexto, las estrategias nacionales de transición energética deberían priorizar la incorporación de tecnologías renovables no convencionales, especialmente energía solar fotovoltaica, así como el desarrollo complementario de generación eólica y geotérmica hacia 2050, promoviendo una matriz eléctrica más resiliente y sostenible.

El escenario de sequía demuestra que depender solo de hidro es riesgoso; por ello, se deben adoptar marcos regulatorios que faciliten el almacenamiento (baterías), la modernización de redes y una planificación robusta que combine solar a gran escala con hidro como respaldo flexible.

Las políticas deben promover inversiones a gran escala en tecnologías competitivas. Se requiere un diseño de política que impulse subastas renovables, acuerdos público-privados y metas anuales de capacidad. Los resultados indican que la energía solar fotovoltaica emerge como la principal tecnología de reemplazo bajo condiciones de reducción de disponibilidad hidroeléctrica, requiriendo metas progresivas de expansión de capacidad de aproximadamente 2 GW para 2030, 6 GW para 2040 y 12 GW para 2050, con el fin de garantizar la confiabilidad del suministro eléctrico, diversificar la matriz energética y reducir los riesgos hidrológicos asociados al cambio climático.

Future Works

Incorporate high-resolution temporal analyses.

Compare Ecuador's transition pathways with other Latin American countries.

Evaluate energy storage technologies to improve system flexibility and renewable energy integration.

Acknowledgements

We would like to express our sincere gratitude to the organizers and supporting institutions of the Energy Modelling Platform for Latin America and the Caribbean 2026 for their guidance, technical support, and capacity-building activities that contributed to the development of this report. Special thanks are extended to Climate Compatible Growth, International Centre for Theoretical Physics, World Bank Group, 2050 Pathways Platform, Universidad Politécnica Nacional, and British Embassy Buenos Aires for promoting collaborative research on sustainable energy planning in the region. We also especially appreciate the valuable guidance and mentorship provided by Fernando Plazas and Guillermo Fernandez throughout the training process and the development of this work.

References

- Chamorro, J. y Mera, E. (2025) «Estudio de la crisis energética en el Ecuador por la dependencia en la generación de energía hidráulica», *Revista Científica INGENIAR: Ingeniería, Tecnología e Investigación*. ISSN: 2697-3693., 8(15), pp. 168-186.
- Howells, M. *et al.* (2011) «OSeMOSYS: The Open Source Energy Modeling System: An introduction to its ethos, structure and development», *Energy Policy*, 39(10), pp. 5850-5870. Disponible en: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2011.06.033>.
- Ministerio de Energía y Minas (2024) «BALANCE ENERGÉTICO NACIONAL». Disponible en: https://www.recursoyenergia.gob.ec/wp-content/uploads/2024/08/BEN_2023-final_compressed.pdf.
- UNDP (2020) *Mesa de bioenergía coordina esfuerzos para promover el aprovechamiento de residuos y reducir emisiones*, *Unidad de las Naciones Unidas para el Desarrollo*. Disponible en: <https://www.undp.org/es/ecuador/noticias/mesa-de-bioenergia-coordina-esfuerzos-para-promover-el-aprovechamiento-de-residuos-y-reducir-emisiones>
- wgaleas (2025) «La transición energética en Ecuador: oportunidades y desafíos hasta 2050», *Economía Tricolor*, 30 mayo. Disponible en: <https://www.bce.fin.ec/economiatricolor/publicaciones/investigaciones/la-transicion-energetica-en-ecuador-oportunidades-y-desafios-hasta-2050/> (Accedido: 17 de mayo de 2026).

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